

Disclaimer: This report is part of a project that has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement number 862568.

Year 1

Year 2

Year 3

Year 4

Year 5

Design of policy related structured interviews (WP7)

Ana Frelih-Larsen (ECOLOGIC Institute)

Milestone number:11

Milestone title: Design of policy related
structured interviews

Lead beneficiary: ECOLOGIC INSTITUTE

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Overview of the milestone

A systematic screening of stakeholders' positions provides the basis for identifying barriers and solutions, visions for transition to reduced pesticide use, and policy options to support the transition.

The milestone is fulfilled through three elements:

- 1) Analysis of stakeholders' contributions to the consultation on the Farm to Fork Strategy

As a first step in gathering stakeholders' positions, a systematic analysis of stakeholders' views on pesticides reductions, and their visions for sustainable plant production was conducted by analysing stakeholders' contributions to the consultation on the Farm to Fork Strategy. A total of 648 responses were submitted to the consultation. Of these, 297 (45.8%) referred to pesticides within their submissions, indicating that pesticide use was seen as an important topic to many actors and this subset of submissions was the subject of analysis.

The stakeholder groups' were clustered in five categories:

Cluster	Name	Description	Examples of participants
1	Environmental non-governmental organisations (NGOs)	Environmentally-led charities	BirdLife, Friends of the Earth, Greenpeace, WWF, Zero Waste Europe
2	'Other' NGOs	Charities whose primary remit relates to human health and other 'non-environmental' concerns	Animal Task Force, Beyond GM, EurEau, ACT Alliance Advocacy to the EU
3	Research	Academic researchers, ThinkTanks and other evidence-led entities	FIBL, Institute for Environmental Policy
4	Agri-Industry/Business	Industry lobbyists, Agrichemical businesses, biocontrol businesses	Europatat, European Cocoa Association, Bayer Crop Science, Biocontrol Switzerland, BASF, CropLife
5	Farmers	Individual farmers and farming unions	British Agriculture Bureau, IFOAM, International Confederation of Beet Growers

This was an additional task that had not been included in the original Description of Work for WP7 but was included to take advantage of the valuable source of information provided by the public consultation on Farm to Fork Strategy¹. This output will be submitted for peer-review as a publication in March 2022 with the title "Discourses on the future of agricultural pesticide use: a critical analysis of the submissions to the Farm to Fork public consultation." The paper abstract is included in Annex 1.

2) Introductory online meeting with EU stakeholders

Moreover, an introductory online meeting with EU stakeholders was organised on 22 June 2021 and used already to gather insights from stakeholders on barriers and solutions. At this event, stakeholders could join the discussions around four topics: Human health, environmental health, toolbox design, and transition pathways. At the end of the event, stakeholders could also sign up to participate in further exchanges and discussions around these thematic topics. The stakeholders that signed up for the 'Transition stakeholder group' agreed to be contacted to participate in individual interviews.

This transition group includes stakeholders from the following organisations:

Organisation	Country
Institute for environment and nature	Croatia
Testbiotech - Institute for Independent Impact Assessment in Biotechnology	Belgium
ADVID/CoLAB Vines&Wines	Portugal
Pesticide Action Network Germany	Germany
European Commission, DG SANTE	EU
Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
The Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Food Safety, Veterinary Sector and Plant Protection	Slovenia

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12183-Sustainable-food-%E2%80%98farm-to-fork%E2%80%99-strategy_en

Direkcija RS za vode	Slovenia
DRAP Centro	Portugal
Danish Crop Protection Association	Denmark
Better Cotton Initiative	United Kingdom
UIPP	France
Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke)	Finland
OFEV	Switzerland
IFOAM Organics Europe	Belgium
Bristol City Council	United Kingdom
PepsiCo	United Kingdom
European Environment Bureau	Belgium
GIZ Fitofarmacije	Slovenia
Ministry of Rural Affairs	Estonia
Bidhan Chandra Krishi Vishwavidyalaya	India
Federal Environment Agency (UBA)	Germany
TIMAC AGRO ESPAÑA	Spain
BASF SE	Germany
Glastuinbouw Nederland	Netherlands

3) Design of structured interviews.

Individual policy related structured interviews will focus on contributing information to deliverables 7.1, 7.2. and 7.3. This change to the work plan is made to avoid stakeholder fatigue and ensure that the same stakeholders contribute to identification of barriers and solutions (D7.1), the vision for end goal of the transition process (D7.2) and the transition pathways (7.3).

A questionnaire has been prepared with questions relating to the visioning and solutions for transition and is attached as Appendix 2. Interviews will be conducted from March 2022 until Autumn 2022. The interviews will be conducted as per the following plan:

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- The questionnaire will be piloted with three stakeholders from different stakeholder groups, and updated if needed
- 15 – 20 EU level interviews will be conducted with EU level stakeholders representing all relevant types of actors in the agri-food supply chain as shown in the graphic below. The same questions will be asked of all interviewees, but the stakeholders will have the option to focus on the aspects / solutions that they focus on in their work.
- Up to 5 interviews per case study country will be conducted and relevant stakeholders selected depending on the thematic focus chosen in the case study (e.g. economics of alternatives, knowledge and research, agronomic solutions, Common Agricultural Policy, authorisation of pesticides).
- The interviews will be conducted via online tools, and at national level in person where Covid circumstances allow.

Annex 1:

Discourses on the future of agricultural pesticide use: a critical analysis of the submissions to the Farm to Fork public consultation.

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Abstract

This paper analyses the submissions of a public consultation concerning the European Union's Farm to Fork Strategy. Based on a critical discourse analysis, we first present different lines of arguments as to why pesticide usage should or should not be reduced and how this should be achieved. The results show that those in favour of reducing pesticides tend to argue on the grounds of 'global health', seeing the flourishing of human health as intertwined with that of ecosystems and social justice. Alternatives are seen to already exist (e.g., agroecological practices) and the problem is the lack of political will and power structures. Those in favour of pesticides refer to food security, by which they mean affordable and plentiful food, distributed through market mechanisms. According to these submissions, it is yet to be proven that a total move away from pesticides would be beneficial and alternatives are seen as impractical or non-existent. We also focus on the contestation of the meanings of certain concepts which are used by participants in different ways, such as 'science' and 'sustainability'. We conclude by considering the utility of such means of public consultation and how such activities can be re-imagined building greater societal legitimacy.

Keywords: Agrichemicals, Agriculture, Democracy, Environment, Health, Participatory democracy

Annex 2: Questionnaire for policy related interviews

Date of interview:

Stakeholder Name & Organisation

Country / or EU level stakeholder:

Type of stakeholder:

Gender:

Form (online, in person) and duration of interview:

A. Goal & vision for sustainable plant protection

1. How do you define 'sustainable plant protection'?

(What management practices does it involve?)

2. How would you measure progress towards sustainable plant protection? How would we know that we have reached the goal of sustainable plant protection?

3. What quantitative and qualitative indicators can define the goal and measure progress?

B. Priority farming systems

4. What are the priority farming systems for reducing reliance on pesticide use? i.e. How would you rank the priority to reduce pesticide use in the following farming systems?

Please choose on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 very low and 7 very high.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Arable - Cereals							
Permanent crops – vineyards							
Permanent crops – orchards							
Permanent crops – olives							
Livestock mixed farms							
Horticulture							
Other: (specify)							

5. Please provide any comments on current levels of pesticide use in different farming systems and priority for action:

For the following questions, please focus the interview on one or two farming systems that the stakeholder is most familiar with.

C. Agronomic alternatives that enable reduced reliance on pesticides

6. What are currently available alternatives? Are these cost-effective and accessible to farmers? If not, why not?

Name of alternative and relevance to farming system	Cost-effective?	Accessible?	Explanation

7. Which alternatives are in the pipeline?

	Alternative and explanation
1	
2	
3	

8. What alternatives are completely missing?

	Alternative and explanation
1	
2	
3	

D. Key changes required to transition towards reduced reliance

Please list the top three for each of the dimensions listed below and be as specific as possible.

9. EU level policy and regulatory framework

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

10. Social and economic relations & supply chain

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

11. Changes in farm level management / availability of alternatives

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

12. Institutional and governance arrangements

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

13. Research and innovation

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

14. Knowledge access

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

15. International trade and governance

	Solution and explanation
1	
2	
3	

E. Windows of opportunity

16. Where do you see the main windows of opportunity until 2025?

17. Where do you see the main windows of opportunity until 2030?

18. Where do you see the main windows of opportunity post 2030?